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Introduction

With disastrous effects on ecosystems, human health, and the economy, plastic pollution has become one of the 21st century's most critical environmental issues. The United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) has responded by starting talks for a global agreement to fully combat plastic pollution. The goal of these negotiations is to reach a comprehensive and legally binding agreement that might transform the global production, use, and management of plastics (United Nations Environment Programme, 2024). The potential success of this treaty lies in states' ability to overcome significant challenges to international cooperation, i.e. economic inequality, competing national interests, and the complexity of governing global environmental issues - similar to the Montreal Protocol (being largely successful) or the Paris Agreement (facing challenges).

In the first section of this paper, I will consecutively analyse the likelihood of states successfully concluding the Global Plastics Treaty by analyzing the issue through three major international relations theories: realism, liberalism, and constructivism. Realism considers the state's interest and relative gains as the most influential aspects shaping state behaviour and compliance with international organisations (Mearsheimer, 2017). Liberalism, on the other hand, puts economic interdependence, cooperation and the possibility of absolute gain on the pedestal of international cooperation (Keohane, 1984). And finally, the constructivist approach focuses on the significance of norms and shared values in shaping international action (Wendt, 1995).

In the second section, I will delve into how states could best design the compliance system for the Global Plastics Treaty, considering theories of non-compliance in world politics. Analysing and applying managerial and enforcement model will help us draw conclusion about the compliance model best suited for GPT. However, the case study of successful Montreal Protocol will be core in drawing those recommendations for building and monitoring compliance.

PART I

Discuss the likelihood of states successfully concluding an ambitious treaty to end plastic pollution, contrasting realist, liberal, and constructivist understandings of the conditions under which international cooperation is likely to be established.

Realism

The core principles of realism, as Mearsheimer (2017) highlights, are that states behave primarily in their own self-interest to ensure survival and security within the international system with no overarching authority to enforce agreements in the anarchic international system. In this self-help system, states prioritize maintaining or increasing their power relative to others, focusing on relative gains rather than absolute gains. This dynamic drives states to view international cooperation cautiously, particularly when it may jeopardise their strategic position. Furthermore, realism strongly emphasises the importance of state sovereignty, claiming that states are unlikely to hand out authority to international organisations if such actions contradict their national interests or undermine their sovereignty.

Looking at the data one of the main ambitions of the Global Plastic Treaty is the “Circular plastic economy” to enhance the life-cycle of plastic. The basic notion lies in the reusing and recycling of plastic (UNEP, 2024). OECD, in 2022, concluded in a report, that even though the demand to reduce plastic production was large, only 8% of all plastic lifecycle was circular. Furtherly, in 2019, only 15% of plastic was collected and 9% actually recycled. From a realist perspective, the likelihood of the adoption of such a treaty might be challenged by major powers and producers of plastic. China, for example, being the largest producer and exporter of virgin plastics, accounted for 33% of global plastic material production in 2019, the rest of Asia (mainly India) another 19%, and North America 17% (Statista, 2024). Agreeing to such a treaty, where the main goal is the ‘circular plastic lifecycle’ and cuts in plastic production would harm the economies and national interests of major powers. As argued by Chey (2024), the efficiency of GPT is heavily dependent on China. This opens the argument for the second challenge the treaty faces under the realist approach. UNEP and Intergovernmental Negotiating Committee (INC), as an international institution, serve as a power projection for powerful states (Mearsheimer, 2017), which might, essentially based on the principles of the realist approach, shape the treaty to protect and enhance their own interests. The third challenge is that states may perceive environmental agreements as zero-sum, where other states might gain

economically if one state adopts measures to reduce plastic production and other states would not.

Historically, environmental treaties have often been limited in effectiveness when national interests conflict with global goals. For example, the Kyoto Protocol or Paris Agreement, where states prioritized national interest and economic advantages over environmental issues. Kyoto Protocol, where the U.S. did not ratify the agreement, and developing countries at that time – China, India, Indonesia etc. increased GHG emissions rapidly, and the Paris Agreement, where under Trump's presidency, the major power, the U.S. withdrew from the agreement.

From a realist perspective, the likelihood of states concluding GPT is low, unless the major powers perceive that failing to address plastic pollution directly threatens their national interests. The anarchic nature of the international system, conflicting national interests, and concerns about relative gains present significant obstacles. Realists argue that GPT will only succeed if powerful states perceive immediate threats to their interests, national security or economic stability, from failing to address plastic pollution.

Liberalism

Liberalism, similarly to the realist approach, acknowledges the anarchic international system but argues that institutions can facilitate cooperation by reducing transaction costs, increasing transparency, and providing enforcement mechanisms. Unlike realism, liberalism and rational functionalism, which originated from Keohane's *After Hegemony* (Martin & Simmons, 2012), proposed that "individually rational action by states could impede mutually beneficial cooperation" (p. 331). This fundamentally different approach to international relations and cooperation suggests that mutual cooperation through institutions might provide gains for more actors. The general rationale is as follows: if states trust each other (no security dilemma as in realism), they are able to develop absolute gains - benefits all states can achieve collectively rather than competition over relative advantages (Keohane, 1984).

In this sense, UNEP is an institution created for negotiation, mediation and development of frameworks for collective actions in the area of environment. States, being economically interdependent, will eventually adopt the GPT, as plastic pollution can disrupt trading routes and fisheries or potentially destroy tourism. GPT potentially benefits all states, as plastic pollution can lead to economic losses, which might be larger than the costs of transforming

plastic production. Liberalism argues that states are motivated to cooperate because addressing these shared challenges offers collective benefits. What makes the likelihood of adoption of GPT through the lenses of liberalism, is the role of NGOs and pressure on a domestic level. Plastic Free Foundation, according to SC Johnson, found out that 88% of polled people are in favour of such a Treaty, more the 80% polled, from different age groups, consider plastic pollution as significantly harmful (2024), and the adoption of the treaty is backed up by more than 275 organisations have become part of so-called Business Coalition for a Global Plastic Treaty (BCGPT, n.d.), putting significant pressure for governments to adopt ambitious positions during treaty negotiations.

The potential for successful international cooperation is demonstrated through lessons gathered from previous agreements, such as the Montreal Protocol. The Montreal Protocol, which successfully tackled the damage to the ozone layer by gradually eliminating dangerous chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs), serves as a benchmark for environmental treaty success. The scientific consensus, and access of scientists to the treaty negotiations, clear objectives of the treaty and mechanisms that encouraged compliance, such as trade restrictions on non-participating states, were key to the success of the Montreal Protocol, according to Barratt-Brown (1991). Bearing this in mind, the key role of scientists in defining the key objectives is crucial, however, scientists had a hard time accessing the negotiations, mainly due to the capacities of venues, according to Nature Editorial (2024). Furtherly, some sources, according to Nature Editorial, stated, that some parts of negotiations were made in closed groups.

Concluding, the likelihood of the adoption of GPT, building on the success of the Montreal Protocol, is high. However, negotiation must be more transparent, open and cooperative.

Constructivism

Constructivism emphasizes that state behavior is shaped by shared norms, values, and identities rather than material interests alone. Constructivist scholars argue that international institutions have the ability to change the norms and identities of actors, under the set of rules and through time (Martin & Simmons, 2012). Unlike realists or liberals, the analysis itself is more open as “ the relevant actors, their interests, and their understandings of rules and relationships are all open to interpretation” (p. 335). Meaning, that rising global concern about plastic pollution, interpreting plastic pollution as a common threat pushes states to act. This analytical take-out

also works the other way around, how states are perceived by other states, societies and businesses, can shape the way states would act.

We can look again at the example of the Montreal Protocol, where ozone layer damage was framed as a global threat by scientists, where this scientific consensus about a threat and solution subsequently led to an awareness of the masses about this issue. This shaped the behaviour of states in favour of the Montreal Protocol, even for the price of slight economic disturbances. On the other hand, the Paris Agreement dealing with the climate crisis and the goals to reduce the impacts and reasons for the '1.5 Celsius' limit, was framed by major powers as 'unimportant'. Moreover, the framing on social media and politicians led to high scepticism about the climate crisis among masses reducing the incentive for states to act.

We can see two different poles, examples, however, for constructivists, how reality is interpreted is key to what action will be taken. From a constructivist perspective, the likelihood of states agreeing to the GPT is dependent on how this issue will be framed, however, we can say based on the polls about people's opinions about plastic pollution (mentioned in the section on liberalism), that the likelihood is moderate to high - depending on how effectively norms around sustainability and responsibility are promoted. If states internalize the idea that fighting plastic pollution is a global moral duty and advocacy networks maintain pressure, cooperation is likely. However, achieving consensus may take time, especially with resistance from states tied to the plastics industry e.g. China, the U.S., India etc.

PART II

Concluding a new treaty also entails setting up a system for ensuring compliance with its rules. Discuss how states could best design the compliance system for the Global Plastics Treaty, considering theories of non-compliance in world politics.

Managerial model of compliance and GPT

The success of treaties relies on mechanisms which ensure compliance with them.

It is argued that if treaties are at the heart of cooperative regimes, mechanisms must be in place to ensure parties fulfil their obligations. While coercive enforcement measures can play a role, relying on coercion as a long-term approach has been proven to not be effective. Instead, a managerial model is often proposed, where non-compliance is understood as a management problem, addressing non-compliance by helping states overcome technical, financial, or institutional challenges rather than sanctioning states (Chayes & Chayes, 1995). In managerial school the noncompliance, when it occurs, is not viewed as deliberate defiance or exploitation of the treaty (Downs et al., 1996). It is rather attributed to the ambiguity of the treaty – language used is vastly vague, limited capacities of the states to meet the obligations – states might not have the capacities to comply, and unpredictable social or economic changes that make compliance difficult (Chayes & Chayes, 1995). The managerial model approach to ensure compliance with GPT is relevant, as it motivates developing states to come to the treaty – as they do not possess the capacities to ‘transform’ their infrastructure as quickly as developed states.

GPT produces procedural challenges to states to fully comply with it (potentially, if it is adopted), i.e. technical challenges, infrastructural challenges, technological capacities etc. The managerial model is much useful in addressing those challenges, as it assures fairness and inclusivity in the sense, that states facing these challenges will not be sanctioned, but rather provided with the necessary capacities to overcome them. Namely, it could be financial support (e.g. funding for waste management systems); technological support (e.g. recycling innovations), or exchange of expertise and personnel in plastic pollution management. Furtherly, the managerial model, according to Chayes & Chayes (1995), emphasises not only the importance of cooperation, negotiations to address disagreements, technical and financial support over sanctioning and punishment but also highlights the importance of transparency

and cooperation in monitoring to identify compliance challenges early and address them collaboratively.

On the other hand, the managerial model, even avoiding coercion, encouraging cooperation, and enhancing the legitimacy of the treaty by procedural mechanisms (resolving disputes during the negotiations), faces several challenges. Downs et al. (1996), argued, that this model leads to states adopting treaties which do not require large changes in behaviour, and treaties which are easier to comply. Furtherly, states might exploit the assistance to fulfil their obligations towards the treaty by misleading the data and monitoring mechanisms. In this sense, the managerial model is largely liberal and it might be challenging for this model to be an effective compliance mechanism in times, where states are beginning to act more realistic.

Enforcement model and GPT

The enforcement model, unlike the managerial one, is moving from liberalism towards realism. Tallberg (2002) summarises that the enforcement model considers states as rational actors whose compliance is determined by cost-benefit calculations, creating incentives to deviate. The incentive to deviate rises when the benefit of deviating is bigger than the cost of detection. Downs et al. (1996), argued that non-compliance is not merely rooted in the ambiguity of the treaties or limited capacities of the states to fulfil the obligations towards it, as the managerial model suggests, but non-compliance occurs for more pragmatic reasons – self-interest of states, and their exploitations of the treaties. The enforcement model, therefore, suggests simply monitoring and sanctioning mechanisms, within which the likelihood of compliance increases by increasing the “likelihood and costs of detection” and sanctions (Tallberg, 2002, p. 611). As Downs et al. (1996) indicated, reversely, high compliance rates with no present sanctioning mechanisms occurred within ‘shallow treaties’ which do not challenge the status quo. This “depth-of-cooperation” hypothesis by Downs et al. simply suggests that the more treaties require a state to change its behaviour, the more incentive it is to deviate by that state. Meaning that more robust sanctions and effective monitoring mechanisms must be implemented (1996).

Realists’ core assumption is anarchic world with no central authority to maintain order within states, necessitates the enforcement mechanisms to maintain compliance with international treaties. Realism emphasizes the central role of power in ensuring compliance, with major powers often taking the lead in enforcing treaty obligations. These powerful states possess the resources, influence, and leverage to impose penalties or apply pressure on non-compliant

states. Enforcement mechanisms i.e. trade restrictions or sanctions (as in the case of the Montreal Protocol) act as important deterrents, making non-compliance too costly for states. Even in anarchic international systems where self-interest dominates, these methods force states to comply with treaty obligations. Furthermore, a fundamental realism idea, relative gains, is addressed by enforcement mechanisms. Enforcement ensures that no state disproportionately benefits at the expense of others, maintaining fairness and stability in the international regime.

To put the enforcement model into practice, GPT can maintain accountability through enforcement mechanisms such as penalties for non-compliance or trade restrictions could be implemented. These measures act as deterrents, encouraging states to follow to the treaty's obligations by making non-compliance too costly to pursue. In the context of the GPT, the role of major powers such as the United States, China, India becomes critical. These actors can leverage their influence to enforce compliance and shape the treaty's rules and mechanisms. However, the question arises, how to ensure the ratification of GPT by these major powers within the enforcement model, if, as empirically proved in Part I, they are being the largest producer and exporter of virgin plastics (Statista, 2024). Although plastic production and export by major powers remain still large, those states did undergo certain technical transformations, due to both consumer health protection, but importantly, because of international environmental concerns (Textor, 2024).

The GPT advantages significantly from empirical lessons learnt from previous agreements. For example, the Kyoto Protocol established mechanisms for compliance, such as sanctions for exceeding emissions targets. However, insufficient enforcement and a lack of support from key stakeholders hindered the effectiveness of these efforts. In contrast, trade agreements governed by the World Trade Organization (WTO) demonstrate stronger enforcement mechanisms, such as dispute resolution systems, where once negotiations to settle a dispute are not efficient, the report by the panel is issued. Once a member state fails to adhere the obligations, trade restrictions or sanctions are implemented (European Commission, n.d.). However, as argued before, major powers will play a crucial role in adhering to the treaty, however, it will be important to ensure their compliance in the first place – as they are self-interested and rational actors.

Montreal Protocol mechanism as a model for GPT

We now stand in between the managerial – problem-solving model and enforcement – monitoring-sanction model (Tallberg, 2002). Using the Montreal Protocol (as a case study for its reputation for effective compliance mechanisms and goal reached is particularly useful for GPT. Montreal Protocol, being vastly successful in reversing the destruction of the ozone layer, was adopted in 1987 and gained recognition and strength in 1990 under the UNEP. By 1990, 63 countries producing 99% and consuming 90% of all chlorofluorocarbons combined ratified the treaty (Benedick, 1989). This was significant for the overall success of the Montreal Protocol (Barratt-Brown, 1991).

How was the compliance regime under the Montreal Protocol built and monitored, and what lessons can GPT draw? Using an amazing study by Barratt-Brown (1991), where she not only explains the mechanisms but also draws implications from human rights regimes, ILO and Nuclear non-proliferation regimes. She argues that three factors must be at the core of any effective compliance regime. “Integration of NGOs in negotiating processes, verification of compliance, and open and routine monitoring” (p. 564).

The role of NGOs. NGOs in treaty negotiations (current stage of GPT) shall represent the public and not the interests of respective governments. The incorporation of NGOs and industrial representatives into both building and monitoring of a compliance regime provides larger expertise and, similarly to the regime of ILO requiring states to nominate a delegation from the nongovernmental sector according to “past or potential contributions to domestic or international progress” (p. 565) in the respected field. Moreover, if NGOs are not selected by their home country, they should have a possibility to directly appeal to UNEP. Currently, the INC meeting has limited capacity for scientists and NGOs, which might create a burden to fulfil the first of three factors of an effective compliance regime, in respect of the Barratt-Brown framework. Nonetheless, a governing body consisting of developing and developed member states, NGOs, industrial representatives and scientists shall be constituted, with regular meetings to amend, review compliance, report, and make progress. Such as in the Montreal Protocol, no member shall possess veto power, which encourages members to propose amendments. According to Barratt-Brown (1991), annual meetings of the members have come with enormous importance.

Creating a monitoring and sanctioning mechanism. GPT is well-structured for similar monitoring and sanctioning mechanisms as the Montreal Protocol. GPT shall create a permanent body to monitor and report compliance at the annual meetings. The establishment of a non-confrontational compliance committee is a fundamental component of the Montreal Protocol approach. This committee maintains the parties' compliance in fulfilling their treaty obligations, identifies cases of non-compliance, and addresses them. The committee focuses on supporting states in resolving compliance issues through technical support, capacity-building initiatives, and plans rather than enforcing immediate sanctions. This managerial approach has been essential to preserving and maintaining trust and participation among all parties.

On the other hand, the Montreal Protocol consists of strong enforcement mechanisms, and trade restrictions, ensuring the adherence with the treaty obligations. States agreed to reduce the trade of CFCs with non-signatory parties to the treaties. This measure acts as a powerful deterrent, as it makes non-compliance economically costly (Barratt-Brown, 1991). Barratt-Brown (1991), furtherly suggests a committee for non-compliance hearings, an implementation committee – for evaluation of compliance, a committee to review state reports, and a court for a state to appeal the recommendations of the committees. However, trade restrictions shall apply in case of non-compliance. The framework proposed serves as a trust-building and impartial body to ensure compliance. Committees shall consist of experts to command objective authority. Regular reporting of all committees is particularly important for it provides complex analysis of compliance of member and non-member parties to the treaty, upon which committees shall provide recommendations for states.

Conclusion

Global Plastic Treaty is not the only significant treaty discussed under the UNEP. As mentioned, the Montreal Protocol has been vastly successful in reducing CFC production and reversing the destroying of the ozone-layer, mainly for the compliance model set in the treaty. If we were to place it within our theoretical framework, it would fall as an effective interplay between realist and liberal approach consisting of both the managerial model and enforcement model. What will be particularly important for GPT will be to not only draw lessons from successful treaties, but also learn from unsuccessful treaties where the compliance model was wicked, or treaties were just exploited by states (as Dawns et al., 1996 would argue). Indeed,

it is important to raise awareness among people about plastic pollution, which then creates leverage for domestic governments, which want to appeal to domestic audiences – framing plastic pollution as a crucial international issue (Dai, 2005). In conclusion, the hybrid approach of managerial and enforcement model with correct framing of plastic pollution is recommended.

For further analysis of the compliance model suited for GPT, we could not only involve ‘lessons drawn’ from the Montreal Protocol, but also, it would be particularly interesting to involve another section ‘lessons learned’ from environmental treaties, that have been vastly exploited by states, or simply lack compliance. Analysing the reasons and compliance mechanisms while using isomorphism could be useful for GPT and its setting of compliance mechanisms.

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